

Field screening of stem borer resistance in new plant type lines

L.M. Sunio, Entomology and Plant Pathology Division, IRRI; R. Caldo, Philippine Rice Research Institute (PhilRice), Maligaya, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines; and M.B. Cohen, IRRI E-mail: m.cohen@cgiar.org

IRRI is developing rice varieties with higher yield potential by changing rice architecture to match an ideotype known as the new plant type (NPT) (Peng et al 1994). The features of the NPT include fewer and larger tillers, all of which are productive; sturdy stems; and erect, deep green leaves. At the IRRI Experiment Station, some plots of NPT lines have been highly damaged by stem borers, particularly by striped stem borer (SSB) *Chilo suppressalis* (Walker). We conducted a field screening of NPT lines and existing IRRI varieties to compare levels of stem borer damage. We also examined the relation of tiller number and silica content to stem borer damage.

Screening was conducted at IRRI (Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines) and PhilRice (Maligaya) during the 1998 dry season (DS, February to May). Thirty NPT lines and three IRRI varieties (IR62, which is relatively susceptible to SSB; and IR64 and IR72, which are moderately resistant to stem borers) were transplanted in plots of 100 plants (5 rows of 20 plants) in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Numbers of tillers and deadhearts (DH) were scored at 39 d after transplanting (DAT) at IRRI and 60 DAT at PhilRice. Numbers of panicles and whiteheads (WH) were scored at 85 DAT, at which time the shorter duration lines were close to harvest and the longest duration lines were at hard dough stage. At WH sampling, 20 plants from each replicate plot were removed and dissected to count the number of larvae and pupae of SSB, yellow stem borer (YSB, *Scirpophaga incertulas* [Walker]), gold fringed stem borer (GFSB, *Chilo auricilius* Dudgeon), and pink stem borer (PSB, *Sesamia inferens* [Walker]). An additional five plants from each replicate plot at the IRRI site were removed and analyzed for silica content (Yoshida et al 1976).

There was substantial variation in levels of DH and WH among NPT lines (see table). Many lines did not differ significantly from IR64 or IR72 in %DH or %WH, while other lines had much higher damage. This result suggests that there may be potential for improving stem borer resistance in the NPT by further selection or breeding with NPT lines that show lower damage in screening trials.

The values of %WH were negatively correlated with the number of productive tillers per hill for both IRRI ($r = -0.38$, $df = 31$, $0.05 > P > 0.01$) and PhilRice sites ($r = -0.64$, $df = 31$, $P < 0.01$). When only NPT lines were included in the analysis, the correlation between number of productive tillers and %WH was not significant for the IRRI site ($r = -0.11$, $df = 28$, $P > 0.05$) but was highly significant for PhilRice ($r = -0.78$, $df = 28$, $P < 0.01$). The fact that the number of productive tillers accounted for such a high proportion of the variation in %WH indicates that the results should be interpreted with caution. The most resistant entries may be those with a low %WH despite having less productive tillers per hill, such as IR66738-118-1-2 and IR65600-27-1-2-2.

The negative correlation between tiller number and %WH may be partly because varieties with fewer tillers tend to have larger tiller diameter (Peng et al 1994). Some studies have found a positive correlation between stem diameter and stem borer susceptibility (Chaudhary et al 1984, Ntamos and Koutroubas 2000).

SSB accounted for >90% of larvae and pupae recovered from dissected plants of 11 entries at IRRI, with the exception of IR62 (79%) and IR64 (76%) (see table). YSB and PSB were of approximately equal abundance in plants dissected at IRRI, while GFSB was not common (data not shown). At PhilRice, SSB was also the most com-

mon species recovered (see table), followed by PSB. IR62, IR64, and IR72 were among the entries with the lowest proportion of SSB recovered at PhilRice. These results are surprising because YSB is usually the most abundant stem borer in tropical wetland rice (Shepard et al 1995). Our results are consistent with earlier observations at the IRRI Experiment Station that NPT lines may be more attractive or suitable hosts to SSB than existing IRRI varieties.

A positive correlation between stem borer resistance and silica content has been reported in some studies (Chaudhary et al 1984). In our study, the silica content of entries fell within a narrow range (5.44–6.78%) and did not differ significantly among entries (see table). There was no correlation between silica content and %DH ($r = -0.19$, $df = 31$, $P > 0.05$) or %WH ($r = -0.03$, $df = 31$, $P > 0.05$).

References

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Evaluation of new plant type lines and IRR1 varieties for stem borer resistance at two Philippine sites, 1998 DS.^a

Entry	IRRI						PhilRice				
	Vegetative stage		Reproductive stage				Vegetative stage		Reproductive stage		
	Tillers (no.)	% DH ^b	Productive tillers (no.)	% WH ^b	% SSB ^{c,d}	Silica content (%)	Tillers (no.)	% DH ^b	Productive tillers (no.)	% WH ^b	% SSB ^{b,d}
IR65564-22-2-3	11.9	12.9 (20.7)	9.8	34.0 (35.6)	94.5 (9.7)	5.6	13.0	19.6 (26.2)	10.4	38.0 (38.0)	60.5 (52.2)
IR65564-44-2-3	10.3	5.2 (12.8)	8.9	15.9 (23.2)	97.0 (9.8)	6.3	15.7	19.9 (26.5)	9.3	35.3 (36.3)	70.7 (58.3)
IR65564-44-5-1	10.4	7.5 (15.7)	10.0	31.4 (34.0)	97.0 (9.8)	5.5	14.6	16.4 (23.6)	11.8	29.4 (32.7)	74.4 (60.8)
IR65597-29-3-2-3	10.3	10.3 (18.2)	6.5	37.6 (37.8)	96.2 (9.8)	6.2	11.3	18.8 (25.2)	9.4	36.8 (37.3)	88.4 (70.9)
IR65598-112-2	9.8	11.2 (19.0)	5.0	31.3 (33.7)	99.2 (10.0)	6.4	13.7	24.4 (29.5)	7.0	41.5 (40.0)	79.0 (63.0)
IR65600-1-2-3	8.6	9.2 (17.3)	5.8	60.0 (50.9)	97.0 (9.8)	5.8	11.7	23.7 (29.0)	7.6	40.6 (39.3)	77.2 (62.0)
IR65911-127-6-2-3	10.6	12.3 (20.5)	6.3	36.1 (36.8)	97.6 (9.9)	5.7	13.1	29.5 (32.8)	7.6	35.1 (36.1)	79.7 (63.4)
IR65600-27-1-2-2	9.2	14.9 (22.6)	7.3	29.1 (32.6)	96.2 (9.8)	6.5	12.0	13.4 (21.3)	8.7	20.3 (26.4)	72.5 (58.6)
IR65600-32-4-6-1	10.6	10.2 (18.4)	7.3	27.1 (31.3)	97.2 (9.9)	6.2	14.5	25.6 (30.1)	8.1	32.0 (34.3)	71.0 (57.5)
IR65600-38-1-2-1	10.8	7.2 (15.4)	6.2	28.7 (32.4)	98.3 (9.9)	6.4	12.8	21.0 (27.0)	8.6	33.4 (35.2)	68.8 (56.6)
IR65600-42-5-2	10.2	8.0 (16.1)	9.9	35.8 (36.7)	97.6 (9.9)	6.2	14.5	18.9 (2.7)	11.4	27.9 (31.7)	81.6 (64.8)
IR65600-54-6-3	9.9	6.2 (14.1)	9.5	36.1 (36.9)	96.8 (9.8)	6.8	14.2	19.8 (26.3)	11.1	29.5 (32.9)	78.0 (62.2)
IR65600-77-4-2-1	9.0	13.1 (20.7)	7.0	30.7 (33.6)	98.5 (9.9)	6.1	12.9	21.9 (27.9)	9.8	29.6 (32.9)	80.5 (64.2)
IR65600-85-1-1	11.5	11.4 (19.5)	7.9	27.1 (31.2)	92.7 (9.6)	6.3	15.8	26.5 (30.9)	9.1	49.0 (44.4)	72.7 (58.7)
IR65600-87-2-2-3	11.1	9.0 (17.4)	8.5	36.0 (36.8)	97.1 (9.9)	6.3	15.1	23.7 (29.1)	9.1	44.4 (41.7)	63.3 (53.2)
IR65600-95-4-5	11.7	14.3 (21.6)	7.1	19.5 (25.6)	97.8 (9.9)	5.8	17.4	23.1 (28.7)	10.1	28.5 (32.1)	58.6 (50.1)
IR65600-96-1-2-2	11.3	10.3 (18.0)	7.1	21.8 (27.6)	98.4 (9.9)	5.4	17.8	20.4 (26.6)	12.5	23.7 (29.1)	62.1 (52.4)
IR65601-35-6-2-3	9.0	9.1 (17.0)	7.8	43.7 (41.3)	98.1 (9.9)	6.5	13.5	19.8 (26.2)	8.2	37.2 (37.5)	62.7 (52.9)
IR65601-52-2-3	10.2	11.8 (19.2)	8.9	33.1 (34.9)	98.2 (9.9)	6.3	15.5	20.0 (26.5)	8.4	40.8 (39.6)	78.0 (63.8)
IR66-158-38-3-2-1	11.8	9.9 (18.3)	9.2	40.6 (39.6)	96.6 (9.8)	6.2	14.9	20.2 (26.6)	10.1	44.2 (41.6)	78.0 (62.4)
IR66159-164-5-3-5	10.6	10.7 (18.2)	10.5	35.7 (36.3)	96.8 (9.8)	5.4	14.5	18.6 (25.5)	12.5	30.2 (33.1)	82.0 (65.2)
IR66159-189-5-5-3	10.1	7.7 (15.6)	9.6	35.8 (36.7)	98.8 (9.9)	6.2	17.0	19.9 (26.3)	14.3	24.1 (29.2)	68.7 (56.2)
IR66160-121-4-1-1	11.6	6.8 (15.0)	12.4	17.8 (24.8)	90.4 (9.5)	6.8	15.7	18.2 (25.1)	15.7	15.0 (22.4)	51.4 (45.5)
IR66160-121-4-4-2	11.1	11.3 (19.5)	10.9	15.5 (23.0)	97.4 (9.9)	6.2	14.7	19.2 (25.7)	13.0	16.9 (24.2)	53.3 (47.0)
IR66160-5-2-3-2	11.2	6.7 (14.5)	11.5	34.1 (35.7)	99.3 (10.0)	6.2	15.8	18.9 (25.6)	14.6	20.2 (26.6)	74.6 (59.9)
IR66165-24-6-3-2	12.8	12.1 (20.2)	7.5	36.8 (37.3)	96.6 (9.8)	6.0	15.4	26.3 (30.7)	8.4	46.0 (42.7)	54.0 (47.4)
IR66738-118-1-2	12.9	7.3 (15.5)	7.3	15.1 (22.8)	95.4 (9.8)	6.2	15.7	23.2 (28.7)	8.6	33.7 (35.4)	72.6 (59.1)
IR66750-6-2-1	9.7	7.4 (15.4)	6.0	32.1 (34.1)	97.5 (9.9)	5.9	15.1	26.1 (30.7)	8.3	42.7 (40.7)	68.0 (56.2)
IR67396-16-3-3-1	12.6	6.1 (14.2)	6.7	6.6 (14.3)	97.1 (9.8)	5.5	16.9	17.0 (24.1)	13.6	23.6 (29.0)	48.8 (44.3)

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Entry	IRRI						PhilRice				
	Vegetative stage		Reproductive stage				Vegetative stage		Reproductive stage		
	Tillers (no.)	% DH ^b	Productive tillers (no.)	% WH ^b	% SSB ^{c,d}	Silica content (%)	Tillers (no.)	% DH ^b	Productive tillers (no.)	% WH ^b	% SSB ^{b,d}
IR67962-84-2-2	10.6	11.2 (19.5)	5.9	28.4 (32.1)	99.0 (10.0)	5.9	15.2	27.7 (31.6)	7.4	35.9 (36.8)	69.9 (57.0)
IR62	15.0	5.7 (13.6)	20.6	17.7 (24.8)	79.2 (8.9)	6.3	27.2	19.7 (26.0)	26.9	27.8 (31.7)	42.5 (40.4)
IR64	17.6	10.8 (18.9)	20.6	107 (19.0)	76.3 (8.7)	6.4	21.9	17.8 (24.6)	21.8	13.5 (21.5)	36.4 (36.7)
IR72	13.9	7.0 (15.2)	11.7	16.1 (23.6)	92.1 (9.6)	6.2	29.2	10.1 (17.8)	25.7	17.1 (24.3)	53.5 (46.5)
LSD (0.05)	2.3	5.7	2.3	6.3	0.4	n.s	3.3	5.1	2.3	7.2	14.1
LSD (0.01)	3.0	7.5	3.0	8.3	0.5		4.3	6.8	3.1	9.5	18.7

^aDH = deadhearts, WH = whiteheads. ^bNumbers in parentheses are arcsine-square root-transformed means. ^cNumbers in parentheses are square root-transformed means. ^d% of larvae and pupae in dissected plants infested with SSB.

Effects of simulated pest damage on rice yields

Khiev Bunnarith, Cambodia-IRRI-Australia Project (CIAP), P.O. Box 1, Phnom Penh, Cambodia; G.C. Jahn, Entomology and Plant Pathology Division, IRRI; Pol Chanty and Chhorn Nel, CIAP E-mail: g.jahn@cgiar.org

The types and levels of damage affecting rice yields at different crop stages were evaluated by simulating pest damage. Many plant species have the ability to decrease the negative effects of injury on yield, a process known as compensation (Pedigo 1991). Rice can compensate for stem borer damage at the tillering stage (Rubia 1994). Rice plants, however, do not compensate for cut tillers to the same degree that they compensate for stem borer damage (Rubia 1996).

Four damage simulation trials were conducted from February 1998 to January 1999 in Phnom Penh, Cambodia, using a randomized complete block design with four replications and four treatments per replicate. Each replicate consisted of a concrete basin (2.8 m × 2.4 m surface, 0.6 m deep), filled with soil to a depth of 0.4 m. The NPK rate was the same in all experiments—60-60-30 kg ha⁻¹, applied as 30-30-30 NPK basally and 30-30 NP at panicle initiation (PI). There were 30 seedlings treatment⁻¹ (1 seedling hill⁻¹) at 20-cm spacing. IR66 seedlings (25 d old) and medium-duration CAR11 seedlings (33 d old)

were transplanted. In these experiments, “50% damage” refers to complete removal of half of the leaves or stems, not cutting the leaves or stems in half. The weight and moisture content of each plot’s yield were recorded. Weights were adjusted to 14% moisture and converted to t ha⁻¹. Significant differences in mean treatment yields were detected by ANOVA and LSD with IRRISTAT 4.0.

Removing all of the leaves from seedlings and cutting off 50% of the leaves at tillering did not significantly reduce yields of IR66. Cutting off 50% of the leaves at booting significantly reduced yields. Cutting off 50% of tillers at booting significantly reduced yields of IR66. Cutting off 50% of tillers at stem elongation, however, did not significantly reduce yields. LSD analysis produced an inconclusive result for treatments with all seedlings cut off at water level. Cutting off 100% of stems at the seedling, tillering, or booting stage of IR66 resulted in yields significantly lower than those of undamaged controls. No IR66 seedlings recovered from cutting at ground level in standing water (Table 1).

Cutting off all seedlings at ground level, cutting off all tillers 30 d after transplanting (DAT) at the water surface, and cutting off all tillers at booting at water level significantly reduced yields of CAR11, although some plants showed vegetative recovery (Table 2). Unlike IR66, CAR11 seedlings exhibited some recovery from cutting at ground level in standing water.

The yields in these experiments are typically achieved by Cambodian rice farmers. These results suggest that rice has a considerable capacity to compensate for or recover from drastic damage. Removing all leaves during the seedling stage and 50% of leaves during stem elongation did not reduce yields, while removing 50% of leaves at booting did. A leaf damage of more than 50% by pests is quite rare. This suggests that, before PI, it may not be necessary to manage pests of rainfed rice, which restrict their damage to leaves, except to lower pest density and reduce damage at PI. Likewise, pests that cut tillers such as rats (Jahn et al 1999) are more likely to reduce yields after PI.